

Information, Quantum Probability and Reflection/Refraction Part V Continuity Equation

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In a series of notes we have considered the problem of light moving in the positive x direction hitting a medium along the y axis at $x=0$ and reflecting and refracting. We assumed that light is of the form of a photon which has an energy E which is the same in the incident, reflected and refracted beams. We also considered the notion of a steady state stream. Given a single photon in the incident beam, it has a probability a to reflect and $1-a$ to refract.

As discussed in previous notes, one may consider an intensity AA , BB , CC for the incident, reflected and refracted rays ($AA>0$ etc) and write energy conservation as: $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ where c_1 is the speed of light in medium 1 and c_2 in medium 2. We noted that the energy conservation equation has two unknowns B, C if A is known, but may be broken into two equations if one considers time removed from the problem (i.e steady state) and one groups by space i.e. $(AA/c_1 - BB/c_1) = CC/c_2$ i.e. $A+B=C$ and $A/c_1 - B/c_1 = C/c_2$. One may note that one does not have a conservation of flux/intensity equation, but that flux/intensity which physically exists is directly linked to energy conservation. One may also note that one does not have an equation of energy flux conservation.

In this note, we consider the dispersion relationship of light $E=pc$ and the notion of a continuity equation which applies to the “square root” probabilities. We consider $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ as the simplest solution, other than a constant and speculate whether $\exp(ipx)$ for a steady state picture represents a kind of square root flux. The idea of a square root flux suggests two sets of equations with square root fluxes which may be multiplied to create a flux equation. $\exp(ipx)$ has a kind of wavelike structure with two dimensions and may interfere. It also maps to a constant flux through $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$. We consider these ideas and conclude that the wavefunction is like a square root flux which helps to associate a picture with the idea of it being a dynamical probability. This is helpful when considering a $W(r$ vector) not equal to $W(r)$ i.e. not spherically symmetric. This suggests unbalanced flux and rotation. In quantum mechanics, one does not have a container and so the fluxes create a static-appearing density in the bound case.

Reflection/Refraction

For a photon moving in the positive x direction hitting a medium along the y axis at $x=0$ and reflecting/refracting, energy is conserved, but two probabilities are introduced, “ a ” to reflect and $(1-a)$ to refract. Thus energy conservation is a given, there are two unknowns “ a ” and $(1-a)$ and one has a physical steady stream/flux scenario. Defining intensities AA, BB, CC (as in (1)) for the incident, reflected and refracted beams (with AA indicating intensity is positive), then energy conservation (a given) may be written (as in (1)) as:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((1))$$

If energy conservation at the photon level is a given, why should one even bother with an energy conservation equation? We argue there is a flux/intensity physically present in the

problem i.e. $AA = n_1 E c_1$ where n_1 is the number of incident photons in a small box, E the energy of a photon and c_1 the velocity. Thus:

$$n_1 = n_2 + n_3 \quad \text{and} \quad E n_1 = E n_2 + E n_3 \quad ((2))$$

It seems, however, that there should be some kind of flux continuity equation in this steady state situation, but ((1)) shows one does not have a flux/intensity conservation equation, $1/c(i)$ values need to be inserted to change to energy.

One may notice that $AA/c_1 = n_1 E/c_1$, but from the photon dispersion relationship:

$$E/c_1 = p \quad ((3))$$

Thus the flux/intensity approach (used to demonstrate energy conservation which is already known without this equation) is linked to the photon dispersion relationship. We wish to examine this relationship more closely.

Photon Dispersion Relationship and the Continuity Equation

The photon dispersion relationship ((3)) is of the form of a wave dispersion relations velocity = frequency*wavelength with wavelike behaviour of light being known in the early 1800s.

Consider the fluid continuity equation: d/dt (partial) density(x,t) + grad dot density velocity(x,t) = 0 ((4))

Here velocity is a fluid velocity vector. Consider ((4)) in 1-dimension. Then using density = $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and velocity(x,t) = c:

$$-E + pc = 0 \quad ((5))$$

((5)), however, is the photon dispersion relationship (which in turn is a wave expression). Thus it seems the fluid continuity equation is linked to wave motion in particular to the photon dispersion relationship if:

$$\text{Unusual density} = \exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((6a))$$

We point out here, however, that one may also use:

$$\text{Unusual density} = \cos(-Et+px) \quad ((6b)) \quad \text{or in fact, any real function of } -Et+px \quad ((6c))$$

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, however, represents a propagating object which is periodic in space and time in keeping with spatial and temporal invariances. $-Et+px$ is a solution, but is completely at odds with these invariances.

(As an aside, one knows from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations that:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} \{ C1 \text{Electric field}(x,t) \cdot \text{Electric field}(x,t) + C2 \text{Magnetic field}(x,t) \cdot \text{Magnetic field}(x,t) \} + C3 \text{grad} \cdot \text{Electric field} \times \text{Magnetic field} = 0 \quad ((6d))$$

where both the electric and magnetic fields behave as $\cos(-Et + p \cdot r)$. Thus $-Et + p \cdot r$ associated with the photon dispersion relationship is closely linked to a continuity equation, but this equation uses $\cos(-Et + p \cdot r) \cos(-Et + p \cdot r)$.

Reflection/Refraction Problem and the Continuity Equation

The reflection/refraction problem involves photons which obey $E = pc$ and so is linked to the continuity equation, yet there is an incident beam, reflected and refracted. Even though a separate continuity equation holds for incident, reflected and refracted photons, the steady state scenario is different. There is no time in the picture, only flux. If the flux represents a kind of dynamic probability that is not changing in time, we suggest considering $\exp(ipx)$ with coefficients A, B, C to be this flux.

From ((1)), AA is the form of flux i.e. some kind of density * velocity. This equation, however, is not sufficient to obtain the coefficients B, C given A. $\exp(ipx)$ is two dimensional and may account for the two dimensions needed to describe directional motion. It may also be linked to two equations if it is considered to be a square root flux/intensity.

In ((1)), AA is constant in space as there exists the same intensity/flux at each x, but $\exp(ipx)$ is a function of x. $\exp(ipx)$, however, is closely linked to a constant, i.e. spatial invariance, because it has a constant modulus. Furthermore, different $\exp(ipx)$ s may interfere which is useful in physically creating damped streams without time present. $A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx)$ is an example of a damped "flux" if B is negative which it is for $n_1 < n_2$. AA - BB is also a damped flux, but ((1)) is an energy conservation equation, not a flux/intensity one.

As noted, intensity/flux is of the form: substance * velocity. For example, AA = $n_1 c_1 E$. What then is $\exp(ipx)$? It seems to be of the form of a square root flux, but also a directionally propagating two dimensional wave like object in the absence of time (although on average the particle moves nonrelativistically as $x = p/m t$). From $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1$ one may suggest that:

$$\sqrt{\text{unusual density} \cdot \text{flow velocity}} = A \exp(ipx) \quad ((7)) \quad (A \text{ may be substituted with B or C})$$

This is unusual because in fluid dynamics one uses intensity, not the square root of it and conservation of various quantities i.e. 1, p, $pp/2m$ with flux. Here there is no conservation of flux (AA) and a conservation of energy ((1)) not conservation of energy flux equation exists. It is the square root (in the sense of $\exp(ipx) \cdot \exp(ipx)$) which represents a self-propagating object which has no time and so exists at all x points, but nevertheless has a direction and is associated with p (momentum). Thus $\exp(ipx)$ is like a dynamical probability linked to steady

state flow and one may suggest that it and its first derivative are continuous. The first derivative brings down “p” which is the photon’s momentum. This seems to have two interpretations. First it is proportional to impulse as $2p = \text{Integral Force } dt$ if a particle reflects with the same momentum. Thus there is continuity of impulse in the flow. Secondly, $p=E/c$ so the derivative equation multiplied by the complex conjugate of the $A \exp(ipx)$ continuity equation using ((7)) implies one has density squared $\cdot c/c E$. This shows how a square root flux equation and its first derivative combine to yield conservation of energy.

This is unusual because in the first derivative equation, E is the full energy (not square root), c is the full speed of light ($p=E/c$), but appears in an equation which contains a square root flux forcing it to be combined with another equation also containing the square root of flux/intensity. This imposition leads to two equations which may be used to solve for the two unknowns B and C. (This is similar to the <Wavefunction Operator Wavefunction> approach of quantum mechanics. We discuss this further in a later section.)

Thus treating $E=pc$ as linked to a continuity equation and choosing the simplest solution (other than a constant) which displays a kind of spatial invariance, leads to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. For a steady state system, one drops $\exp(-iEt)$ and treats $\exp(ipx)$ as $\sqrt{\text{flux}}$. Using the continuities described above:

$$A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) \text{ (LHS)} = \text{(RHS)} C \exp(ip2x) \text{ ((9a)) and}$$

$$pA \exp(ipx) - Bp \exp(-ipx) \text{ (LHS)} = \text{(RHS)} Cp2 \exp(ip2x) \text{ ((9b))}$$

$\exp(ipx)$ seems to be an unusual object, but we suggest it is a dynamical probability. This is why we equate it with unusual density \cdot velocity which represents a kind of flow. $\exp(ipx)$ contains p which automatically suggests motion due to p.

One could set $x=0$, but we prefer to take the complex conjugate of ((9a)) and multiply by ((9b)):

$$A^*A p = B^*Bp + C^*Cp2 \text{ or } A^*A/c1 = B^*B/c1 + C^*C/c2 \text{ ((10))}$$

Thus one may multiply the unusual density by its complex conjugate to obtain a steady state flux/intensity which is constant.

For $\exp(ipx)$, multiplying by the complex conjugate yields:

$$\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1 \text{ ((11))}$$

((11)) is usually interpreted as saying that each x point has the same value, but it may also be thought of as a constant steady flux of particles moving with momentum p. The flux/intensity is 1 everywhere. This we argue is the link with fluid flow.

Particles with Rest Mass

What should be done in the case of particles with rest mass which don't satisfy the photon dispersion relationship? The dispersion relationship is associated with linking t and x . For a steady state scenario one only needs $\exp(ipx)$ as this is considered to be $\sqrt{\text{density} \times \text{velocity}}$. Thus one may formulate a problem with two constant potentials V_1 and V_2 separated at $x=0$ by the y axis and apply the above arguments ((9a)) and ((9b)).

As a different example, consider one dimensional scattering from a potential $V(x)$. For an incident particle moving in the positive x direction with momentum p i.e. $A\exp(ipx)$, there exists a reflected piece with $-p$ i.e. $B\exp(-ipx)$ and a transmitted piece with $C\exp(ipx)$. In this case, p has the same magnitude everywhere because the potential is considered to mainly act near the origin (for example an infinite well sphere). Thus the two continuity equations yield:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) \text{ LHS} = \text{RHS } C\exp(ipx) \quad \text{and} \quad A\exp(ipx) - B\exp(-ipx) \text{ LHS} = \text{RHS } C\exp(ipx) \quad ((12))$$

Taking the complex conjugate of the first and multiplying by the second and using the property of differences of squares, yields:

$$A^*A - B^*B = C^*C \quad \text{or} \quad A^*A = B^*B + C^*C \quad ((13))$$

((13)) seems to be a conservation law for the particle number i.e. a given particle either reflects or refracts. Given that the momentum (and speed is the same everywhere), however, ((13)) is also equivalent to a conservation of flux equation. Thus one does not need to use a photon dispersion relationship $E=pc$ to replace p with E/c in order to obtain the $1/c$ needed to convert a flux into a substance (i.e. energy). This also points to $\exp(ipx)$ being $\sqrt{\text{unusual density} \times \text{velocity}}$ i.e. $\sqrt{\text{flux}}$.

Usually $\exp(ipx)$ in quantum mechanics is considered to be the square root of "probability" i.e. $W^*(x)W(x) = \text{density}(x)$, where $W(x) = \text{wavefunction}$. In classical physics, a density is usually thought of as a static entity, although it may be translating or accelerating. In a classical gas with a potential $V(x)$, the density consists of moving particles, but there is a container wall holding the gas. In quantum mechanics there is no such wall, rather there is a moving flux which creates the density and the wavefunction is the square root in a sense of this flux, but follows continuity equations. As a result, a wavefunction which is not spherically symmetric suggests unbalanced fluxes and overall rotation.

Thus we suggest thinking in terms of fluxes/intensities (as in the case of a continuity equation, although formally different) leads to the notion of a wavefunction as more than a static square root probability. It also gives more of a visual picture than simply calling $\exp(ipx)$ a dynamic probability. It is, but it is directly linked to flux albeit in a kind of square root manner. Thus we suggest there is a kind of unusual link with hydrodynamics, at least qualitatively, but at the wavefunction level.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that light moving in the forward x direction and reflecting/refracting in a steady state manner with the energy of the photon being constant is physically linked to an intensity or flux problem. Energy conservation is a given and there are two probabilities, one for reflection, the other for refraction. Though a flux/intensity, however, is physically present, it is energy not flux which is conserved i.e. $AA/c1 = BB/c1 + CC/c2$ where AA is the incident flux, BB the reflected and CC the refracted. The form AA is used to explicitly show that flux is positive. Furthermore, there are two unknowns B, C if A is known and only one equation. Are there further flux considerations in this problem? Otherwise the information about flux seems to be a unused.

If one examines the photon dispersion relation $E=pc$, it may be linked to the continuity equation: d/dt partial density + d/dx density velocity = 0 in the simplest spatially invariant manner (other than a constant) using $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. One may note that any function of $-Et+px$ is also a solution. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, however, has the form of a propagating object, and is also defined at all t, x points.

In a steady state system with no time we suggest examining $\exp(ipx)$. This has two dimensions and can distinguish the direction of motion. Also $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ which is linked to a constant flux. Thus we suggest thinking of $\exp(ipx)$ as the sqrt of flux and consider its continuity and that of its derivative. Introducing the derivative is interesting because d/dx brings in p which is not a square root value while $\exp(ipx)$ is. Thus one must combine two "square root" equations in order to have an overall one with non-square root values. This leads to two equations (in the square root of flux) (which may be used to solve for two unknowns) linked to a single concept i.e. flux.

We also suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ applies to a particle with rest mass and suggest it be thought of as a dynamical probability or a square root of flux. We consider how fluxes appear in a steady state scattering problem and how $W(\mathbf{r}$ vector) the wavefunction of a bound state shows flux if $W(\mathbf{r}$ vector) is not $W(r)$ i.e. spherically symmetric. Thus instead of thinking of the wavefunction as the square root of a static probability, we suggest thinking of it as the square root of a flux. It is this square root flux, which may interfere to ensure high flux content in certain areas and low in others, which "creates" the bound state density as there is no holding container as in a classical statistical mechanical gas. Furthermore the notion of square root of flux suggests that there are two equations rather than a single flux one.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change